

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SYNONYMOUS AND ANTONYMOUS EXPRESSIONS OF THE CONCEPTS “BEAUTY/UGLINESS” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

I.U.Tojiboyev

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences,
Namangan State University,
itojiboyev363@gmail.com
+998945087713

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18657526>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th February 2026

Accepted: 15th February 2026

Online: 16th February 2026

KEYWORDS

linguistics, concept, antonym, synonym, beauty/ugliness, synonymous relationship, antonymic relationship, parallel phenomena, figurative meaning, original meaning, opposite meaning, graduonymy, strongly, weakly, strong level, weak level.

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the analysis of lexemes representing the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in English and Uzbek languages and the analysis of synonymous and antonymic relationships between them. Synonyms are, to a certain extent, factors that indicate the level of development of a language, its richness. Correctly distinguishing between synonyms and using them correctly in their proper place allows you to clearly express your thoughts, clearly show the attitude of the subject to the object about which he is thinking. When defining synonyms, it is necessary to take into account the original meaning of the word and its meaning realized in the context, as well as its figurative meaning. Antonyms are one of the phenomena that are determined on the basis of the semantic relationship between language units. Defining antonyms, on the one hand, leads to a deeper understanding of the lexical meaning of words, and on the other hand, helps to distinguish the meanings of one word in polysemy, and is also useful in defining synonyms. The article takes a broad approach to this issue using examples.

Introduction

It is known that although research on synonyms has been conducted in linguistics, the ideas expressed in them are often inconsistent. Synonyms are defined in many literatures as “words with the same meaning” or “words with similar meanings.”

Literature review: I.V. Arnold noted that the meaning of a word consists of a main part and a subtle meaning or additional meanings, and that synonyms coincide in the main part of the meaning (I.V. Arnold-1973: 45).

When defining synonyms, working on the basis of the closeness of words in meaning causes a number of confusions. The reason for this is that words have different degrees of closeness in meaning. Some words are very close in meaning to another word, while others are less close in meaning. Some words have different meanings, but in any case, there is a connection between them. Accordingly, if we work on the basis of the closeness of meaning

when defining synonyms, then both words that are very close in meaning to each other, as well as words that are partially close in meaning, should be considered as synonyms.

The distinctive feature of each of the mutually synonymous words is, firstly, that it is different in pronunciation and spelling, and, secondly, that each has its own specific nuance of meaning, additional meanings. Therefore, when defining synonyms, it is necessary to take into account that the meaning that unites them is the same in all of them, that these words are different in spelling and pronunciation, and that they differ from each other in various subtleties of meaning.

Synonyms are, to a certain extent, one of the factors that indicate the level of development of a language, its richness. Correctly distinguishing between synonyms and using them correctly in their place allows you to clearly express your thoughts and clearly show the attitude of the subject to the object about which he is thinking.

When defining synonyms, it is necessary to take into account the literal meaning of the word and its meaning realized in the context, as well as its figurative meaning. Sometimes there are such phenomena in the language that a word is used in a wider range of figurative meanings than in its literal meaning. For example, the word *fox* is very widely used in the meaning of *cunning*. Usually, synonyms arise on the basis of the relationship of more than one, that is, two, three, four, and more language units. It is impossible to limit and determine the number of units participating in such a relationship. Secondly, these language units form a regular system within themselves. Therefore, at least two language units participate in the relationship of synonymy. One of them is synonymous with the other, and all together form a synonymic nest. Synonymy is used to enhance meaning, convey subtle aspects of meaning, and express colorful stylistic nuances. By selectively using one of the synonyms, one aspect of reality is emphasized. In fact, for synonymy to occur, lexical units (as well as grammatical units) must also have differences from each other. When selectively using a word or phrase, these differences must always be taken into account. When expressing a specific thought or attitude, it is necessary to be able to choose the most appropriate word or phrase from the synonymy (R. Rasulov-1989: 96).

Research methodology: Synonyms are used effectively to structure speech fluently, avoid repetitions, and also to eliminate sound (pronunciation) inconveniences. The level of significance of the concept expressed by synonyms varies. Some words in a synonymous series express the significance to a normative degree, while others express it to a stronger or weaker degree.

The phenomena of graduonymy and synonymy differ in their basic features. After all, synonymy is based on the exact relationship of the sememes of two or more lexemes and phrasemes (O. Bozorov-1995: 32). Synonyms can be used one for the other in some places. But not always. For example: *elvizak-shabada-shamol-buron*. In this series, it is not possible to use one for the other. True, in many cases, if the differences in graduonymy between graduonyms are small or weak, the similarity in sememes increases, and this situation causes semantic proximity (semantic exactness, as in synonyms), as a result of which they can be used one for the other in some contexts. Subtle differences in graduonymy in the structure of synonymy are actually peripheral signs of graduonymy (the penetration of graduonymy into synonymy), not of synonymy in essence.

As for the relation of graduonymy and antonymy, these are actually semantic phenomena that rely on the basis. The phenomena of graduonymy and antonymy are formed on the basis of distinctions. In the traditional and currently widespread definition of antonymy, the two poles (bright edges) of a graduonymic series are taken, and the intermediate or adjacent distinction relations of this series are left out of the assessment. We see this, for example, in the gradation series *bad - satisfactory - good - excellent*. At this point, the question rightly arises: If *bad - good* (*good-bad*) are mutual antonyms, how should the remaining relations of this series (*bad - satisfactory*, *satisfactory-good*) be assessed? It goes without saying that all three relations in this series are of the same nature (O.Bozorov-1996:155). Therefore, this series is not wrong, in that we see that *good-bad* has large (strong) differences and forms a strong opposition, while the remaining pairs of *bad-satisfactory*, *satisfactory-good* form weak oppositions (O.Bozorov-1996:157).

Analysis and results: Synonyms and antonyms are parallel phenomena, one does not negate or limit the other. Therefore, each antonym has its own synonym. It is worth noting that studying linguistic phenomena not only from the point of view of synonymy, but also from the point of view of antonymy allows for a thorough and in-depth analysis of this phenomenon.

The feeling of "pretty" in the semantic structures of the words expressing the concepts of "beauty/ugliness" that we studied is primarily human. The same feeling exists in different degrees in different people.

For example, "beauty" If the lexemes *beautiful - lovely - charming - graceful* expressing the concept are synonymous with each other, then *raving beauty - beauty queen - femme fatale - prince charming* are also synonymous according to the meaning they express. For example: *She had lovely (beautiful) hair; There are lots of charming (lovely) little restaurants along the river*)(McMillan-2020:169).

"Ugliness" ugly - *The lexemes unsightly - unseemly - unshapely or graceless - ungraceful* can be synonyms for each other. For example: *Do you think its frame makes the picture look ugly (unsightly)?;*

Unpleasantness - sadness - unhappiness - wretchedness or arching heart-broken heart are synonyms. For example : *Joan's childhood was filled with pain and sadness (unhappiness)*(McMillan-2007:241).

Although the lexical units that represent the concepts we have analyzed are considered synonymous with each other in terms of their meaning, they differ in terms of their use, that is, they are distinguished by varying degrees of strengthening of the same meaning and their specificity to different styles. The intensity scale is useful in revealing the synonymous and antonymic relationships between these words. The word "beauty" that we are analyzing is located at the top of the vertical scale, and "ugliness" is located at the bottom. If we gradually weaken the meaning of the word "beautiful", the feeling of "loveliness" gradually decreases, and eventually the feeling of "ugliness" begins. In other words, beauty gradually turns into ugliness. However, there is also a gradation in the expression of the feeling of "ugliness".

The conclusion is that the meanings of "beauty" and "ugliness" form a chain on a scale of intensity. The feeling of "ugliness" increases from a weak level to a strong level. In other words, the feeling of "ugliness" can also manifest itself in different degrees.

Words that have opposite or contradictory meanings are considered antonyms of each other: *long – short, far – near, right – left, love – hate*. Antonyms by word class are especially common in adjectives and adverbs: *good – bad, beautiful – ugly, wide – narrow, fast – slow and, etc.*

In English, negative prefixes such as *ir-, im-, is-, un-* are added to adjective antonyms. The principle of the logical center should be used appropriately when determining whether a word is an antonym. The point assumed to be the middle of the antonymic poles or the intermediate concept between the concepts expressed by two antonymous words is the logical center. Antonyms are one of the phenomena determined on the basis of the semantic relationship between language units. Determining antonyms, on the one hand, leads to a deeper understanding of the lexical meaning of words, and on the other hand, helps to distinguish the meanings of one word in polysemy, and is also useful in determining synonyms.

It is known that until now, when defining antonyms, the two poles (bright edges) of the series have been taken into account, and the intermediate or adjacent differentiation relations of this series have been left out of the assessment. This is clearly seen, for example, in the series *beautiful - ugly*. At this point, the following question rightly arises: If *beautiful - ugly (ugly - beautiful)* are mutual antonyms, how should the relations existing in this series (*beautiful - hideous, beautiful - grotesque, beautiful - dowdy, beautiful - unshapely*) be assessed?

According to the results of the analysis, we can see that *beautiful - ugly (ugly - beautiful)* has great differences and forms a strong opposition, while others (*beautiful - hideous, beautiful - grotesque, beautiful - dowdy, beautiful-unshapely)* form weak antonymic pairs.

Table 1

Synonymous and antonymic relationships of words expressing the concept of "Beauty/Ugliness" in English

Expression level	Beauty	Ugliness
Strong level	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. charming - very attractive 2. exquisite - extremely beautiful 3. enchantress - extremely attractive 4. beautiful - very beautiful 5. your voice - very beautiful 6. handsome - very attractive 7. magnificent - very impressive 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. hideous-very ugly 2. grotesque-extremely ugly 3. gross-extremely unpleasant 4. loathsome-very unpleasant 5. ghastly-very unpleasant 6. foul-very unpleasant 7. odious-very unpleasant
Weak level	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. graceful- attractive 2. natty- attractive 3. sightly- attractive 4. shapely- attractive in shape. 5. comely- attractive 6. elegant-attractive 7. showy- attractive 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. graceless-not attractive 2. dowdy- not attractive 3. awkward- not attractive 4. unshapely- not attractive 5. unprepossessing-not impressive or attractive 6. inelegant - not attractive. 7. grim- ugly and unpleasant

The words listed next to each other in the table are synonymous, while the words on the opposite side are antonyms.

Such an analysis of the words expressing the concepts of “beauty/ugliness” helps to understand more deeply the subtle synonymous and antonymic relationships between them. Thus, the concepts of “beauty/ugliness” occupy a place in one semantic chain on the intensity scale. The words expressing each concept have a synonymous relationship with the words in their row. Through the table, we also clearly see the antonymic relationships between them. As we noted above, the gradation of the meaning of a word also leads to the formation of weak antonymic relationships.

Table 2
Synonymous and antonymic relationships of words expressing the concept of “beauty/ugliness” in Uzbek

Expression level	Beauty	Ugliness
Strong level	1. go‘zal – juda chiroyli 2. chiroyli - yoqimli 3. suluv - soxibjamol 4. nafis - nozik 5. nazokatli - lozar 6. barno - zebo 7. sarv qomat – alif qomat	1. xunuk - juda xunuk 2. xunuk - yoqimsiz 3. jirkanch - iprisqi 4. ko‘rimsiz - ko‘rksiz 5. ajiva - alvasti 6. badnusxa - badchehra 7. iflos - isqirt
Weak level	1. kelishgan - xushbichim 2. ulug‘vor-hashamatli 3. gulchehra- gul yuz 4. parichehra - pariruxsor 5. fusunkor- farahbahsh 6. ko‘rkam - xushmanzara 7. nozanin- tanoz	1. qo‘pol - beso‘naqay 2. didsiz - farosatsiz 3. chirkin - ko‘rksiz 4. badbashara - badburush 5. irkit - qo‘lansa 6. tasqara – ta‘viya 7. dag‘al - qo‘pol

If the words listed in the table are synonyms, the words on the opposite side are in an antonymic relationship. However, it is worth noting that in the dictionary of antonyms, only “beautiful-ugly” (ugly-beautiful) are listed as antonyms. As we mentioned above, if beautiful-ugly are antonyms, what is the relationship between them? For example, the relationship between beautiful-unsightly, beautiful-badfurush, beautiful-taskara, beautiful-besonaqay, beautiful-alvasti, etc. is not given enough importance. In the dictionaries of antonyms of both languages, when defining antonyms, attention is paid to two bright peripheral members, and the intermediate concepts in between are left out of the assessment. If we approach logically, we believe that if bright peripheral members are strongly antonyms to each other, they can be weakly antonyms with intermediate concepts.

Conclusion: Nowadays, in works on linguistic and cultural studies, we see that great attention is paid to the study of the linguistic landscape of the world, linguistic and cultural concepts, linguistic consciousness, and the linguocultural characteristics of phraseological units. Linguocultural characteristics are inherent in each language, and they reflect the lifestyle, development, and path of development of a particular society. In most genres of folk art, phraseological units express various relationships, phenomena, and events in society. In order to express situations more simply and clearly, images of animals, plants, and birds are used. Each of these is used as a symbol, and through them, the image of people with certain positive and negative qualities is strengthened and embodied. Correctly distinguishing between synonyms and using them correctly in their place allows you to clearly express your thoughts, clearly show the attitude of the subject to the object about which he is thinking. When determining synonyms, it is necessary to take into account the original meaning of the word and its meaning realized in the context, as well as its figurative meaning. Antonym is one of the phenomena that is determined based on the semantic relationship between language

units. Determining antonymy, on the one hand, leads to a deeper understanding of the lexical meaning of words, and on the other hand, it helps to distinguish the meanings of a word in polysemy, and is also useful in determining synonyms.

References:

1. Arnold I.V. Stylistics of the contemporary English language (stylistic decoding). - L.: Prosveshchenie, 1973. - S. 45.
2. Rasulov R. State verbs in the Uzbek language and their obligatory valencies. -T.:Fan, 1989.- P.96.
3. Бозоров О. Ўзбек тилида даражаланиш. – Тошкент: Фан, 1995.– 32 б.
4. Bozorov O. The role of gradonymy in the formation of antonymy and synonymy // Uzbek language and literature. 1996. No. 2 – P. 155 -157.
5. Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners. 2007. -P. 169
6. Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners. -P. 241
7. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 1-жилд, – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2020. – 679 б.

